

Clivia mirabilis Miracle Clivia Lily

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Group: Monocot

Size: 50 to 100 cm in height

Distribution:

Endemic to South Africa, the Miracle Clivia Lily is known to occur in the Oorlogskloof area near the town of Nieuwoudtville in the Northern Cape. The species has only been recorded in the Oorlogskloof Nature Reserve, where two subpopulations are found on the Bokkeveldberge plateau.

Importance:

Clivia mirabilis survives in an unusually arid environment compared with other *Clivia* species, which is why it is known as the “miracle lily”. Its distinctive hardiness has made it desirable for breeders seeking to improve ornamental *Clivia* lines. However, heavy illegal poaching has removed thousands of plants from the wild. This leaves the remaining population dangerously small and at risk of extinction in its natural habitat.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 426.45 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 12.38 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 15.12 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.3% [Single: 69.9%, Duplicated: 29.4%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 1 836.01 kilobases

Contig number: 22 148

Sample Contributor contact details:

Felix Middleton

Clivia Society of South Africa

Felix.middleton@limagrain.com